

Synthesis, reactions and physico-chemical (IR, UV-Visible, FAB-MS and thermogravimetric) studies of new complexes of nickel(II) containing {2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzimidazole moiety[†]

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Abstract : Mono-{2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzimidazole nickel(II) chloride, [(μ -Cl)₂Ni₂{ η^2 -(pbz)}₂] (1) and bis-{2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzimidazole nickel(II), [Ni{ η^2 -(pbz)}₂] (2) have been prepared by the reactions of nickel(II) chloride with {2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzimidazole (pbzH) in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio(s), respectively. Complex 1 was treated with sodium salts of Schiff bases (sb) [sb = smabH, sapH], isopropoxide, aluminiumtetraisopropoxide, aryloxo- and alkoxo-salts in the presence of THF-C₆H₆ to synthesise mixed ligand complexes of the types : [(smab)Ni{ η^2 -(pbz)}] (1a), [(sap)Ni{ η^2 -(pbz)}] (1b), [(μ -OPrⁱ)₂Ni₂{ η^2 -(pbz)}₂] (1c), [(μ -OAr)₂Ni₂{ η^2 -(pbz)}₂] (1d) and [(μ -OPrⁱ)₂Al(OPrⁱ)₂Ni{ η^2 -(pbz)}] (1e). All these new products have been characterised by spectroscopic [IR, Electronic (UV-Visible), FAB-MS], thermogravimetric and magnetic studies.

Keywords : Nickel(II) complexes of {2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzimidazole, synthesis and spectroscopic studies.

Introduction

Due to biological, pharmacological, clinical and analytical applications¹ of transition metal complexes containing Schiff bases and substituted benzoxazole/benzimidazole ligands, we have been interested to synthesise and characterise the mixed ligand complexes of '3d' transition metals during recent past years². The photophysics and photochemistry of these ligands have also been studied by other group of workers³. Our special interest to prepare benzimidazole containing complexes of nickel(II), due to excellent medicinal properties and biological activities of imidazole group⁴ present in the complexes.

Keeping above facts in view, we report herein the synthesis, reactions and characterisation by spectral [IR, Electronic (UV-Visible), FAB-MS], thermogravimetric and magnetic studies of nickel(II) complexes containing {2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzimidazole moiety as a potential ligand alongwith other Schiff bases.

Results and discussion

The nickel(II) complex, [(μ -Cl)₂Ni₂{ η^2 -(pbz)}₂] (1) and [Ni{ η^2 -(pbz)}₂] (2) have been prepared by the interactions of nickel(II) chloride (hydrated) with {2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzimidazole (in refluxing ethanol) in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio(s), respectively, followed by the addition of dilute solution of sodium acetate to produce yellow coloured precipitate, which can be represented by the following reactions :

The complexes 1 and 2 have been digested, filtered and washed with aqueous ethanol and final drying was done

[†]Dedicated to (Late) Professor R. C. Mehrotra – my mentor and Father of Metal Alkoxide Chemistry on his 87th birthday.

at ~100 °C under reduced pressure to produce coloured solids, which are insoluble, non-volatile and polymeric.

The complexes were found to be insoluble in common organic solvents (such as C₆H₆, CCl₄, CHCl₃, *n*-hexane etc). However, the complex **1** can form adduct with THF and pyridine after a long stirring for ~8–12 h, whereas complexes are soluble in DMF, DMSO, THF and pyridine. The mono-{2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzimidazolatonickel(II)chloride, [(μ-Cl)₂Ni₂{η²(pbz)}₂] (**1**) complex was treated with sodium salt of various Schiff bases, soluble coloured complexes were obtained. However, reaction of complex **1** in presence of an excess of proton donor solvents, such as alcohols, leads to disproportionation :

where R = Prⁱ or Buⁿ etc.

The polymeric [(Cl)Ni(OR)]_n product has been separated and characterised by elemental analyses, which corresponds to the reported⁵ value for these complexes. To avoid disproportionation, THF has been used as reaction medium instead of alcohol. The complex **1** was treated with sodium salts of salicylidene-2-aminopyridine, Na(sap) and salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene, Na(smab) in equimolar ratio in the mixture of THF and benzene :

where sb = smabH (**1a**) or sapH (**1b**)

Complex **1** was reacted with Na(OR), [where R = Prⁱ and Ar (Ar = NH₂C₆H₄⁻) in equimolar ratio to produce complexes **1c** and **1d**;

where R = Prⁱ (**1c**) or NH₂C₆H₄⁻ (**1d**)

Further complex **1** was reacted with Na{Al(OPrⁱ)₄} in 1 : 1 stoichiometric ratio to produce a new bimetallic complex of nickel(II) :

All these derivatives are coloured solid and are soluble in organic solvents, which have been purified by

recrystallisation in the mixture of THF-C₆H₆. The synthetic, physical and analytical details are given in Table 1.

IR spectral studies :

Infrared spectrum of newly synthesised chloro complex of nickel(II) containing benzimidazole moiety [(μ-Cl)₂Ni₂{η²(pbz)}₂] (**1**) has been recorded in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ in nujol mull and for lower region, 400–200 cm⁻¹ recorded in KBr pellets. The IR spectrum exhibit structurally significant absorption bands at 470–455 cm⁻¹ for ν_{Ni-N}, 352–348 cm⁻¹ for ν_{Ni-O}, 319–267 cm⁻¹ for ν_{Ni-Cl} and 1602–1579 cm⁻¹ for ν_{C=N}.

The presence of IR absorption bands in the range 470–455 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to ν_{Ni-N} vibrations in the complex. The vibrations in the range 352–348 cm⁻¹ are attributed to ν_{Ni-O} vibration. A band at 275 cm⁻¹ is assigned for ν_{Ni-Cl} bridging vibrations, which is very close to the reported^{6,7} frequency at 265 cm⁻¹ for (μ-Cl)Ni bridging vibrations.

The characteristic IR band for ν_{C=N} group has been reported at ~1615 cm⁻¹ in benzimidazole. The peak for ν_{C=N} was observed at 1579 cm⁻¹ for [(μ-Cl)₂Ni₂{η²(pbz)}₂] (**1**). Shift in frequencies of the complex from that of the ligand suggested the coordination through 'N' atom of C=N group. The N-H stretching frequency observed in the spectra of pure ligand, {2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzimidazole (ν_{N-H} = 3200–3500 cm⁻¹) remains almost unchanged in the complex containing benzimidazole moiety, [(μ-Cl)₂Ni₂{η²(pbz)}₂], which indicates non-participation of the N-H group in coordination. The IR frequencies of the phenolic -OH group of {2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzimidazole is generally observed in the region 1248–1256 cm⁻¹, which get shifted towards 1257–1316 cm⁻¹, thereby indicating the bonding through phenolic oxygen after deprotonation of the phenolic -OH group of the ligand.

The complex **1d** showed shift in the absorption bands in the range 1285–1270 cm⁻¹, which is indicative of bond formation between metal and phenolic oxygen⁸. The complexes, **1c** and **1d** exhibited frequencies in the range 1030 cm⁻¹ and 1150 cm⁻¹ characteristic for ν_{(C-O)Ni} respectively. The bands observed at ~1150 cm⁻¹ is possibly due to terminal isopropoxy groups⁹ and the bands at 1040 and 950 cm⁻¹ are characteristic for bridging isopropoxy groups. Further the bands at 700 cm⁻¹ and 430 cm⁻¹ have been assigned for ν_{Al-O} and ν_{Ni-O}, respectively.

Electronic spectral studies :

The complexes of nickel(II) exhibit two common geometrical forms, octahedral and tetrahedral/square

Table 1. Synthesis, reactions and analytical data of nickel(II) complexes

Sl. no.	Reactants (g. mmol)	Products Found (Calcd.), yield (%)	Melting point (°C)	Nature	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					
					Ni	C	H	N	Cl	Al
1.	NiCl ₂ .6H ₂ O + Hpbz (3.392, 14.3)	[(μ-Cl) ₂ Ni ₂ {η ² -(pbz)} ₂] (1) 4.250 (4.329), 98 solid	350-353 ^a	Dark brown powdered	19.19 (19.33)	51.35 (51.40)	2.88 (2.97)	9.12 (9.23)	12.11 (11.69)	-
2.	NiCl ₂ .6H ₂ O + Hpbz (0.371, 1.56)	[Ni{η ² -(pbz)} ₂] (2) 0.709 (0.744), 95 solid	240 ^d	Yellow powdered	12.21 (12.30)	65.51 (65.45)	3.65 (3.78)	11.80 (11.75)	-	-
3.	1 + Na(smab) (0.300, 0.99)	[(smab)Ni{η ² -(pbz)}] (1a) 0.465 (0.473), 98 solid	305-307	Green powdered	12.08 (12.27)	67.91 (67.60)	4.10 (4.38)	8.92 (8.76)	-	-
4.	1 + Na(sap) (0.300, 0.99)	[(sap)Ni{η ² -(pbz)}] (1b) 0.400 (0.460), 87 solid	300	Brown powdered	12.35 (12.61)	64.70 (64.35)	3.70 (3.86)	11.93 (12.01)	-	-
5.	1 + Na(OPr ^t) (0.300, 0.98)	[(μ-OPr ^t) ₂ Ni ₂ {η ² -(pbz)} ₂] (1c) 0.320 (0.372), 86 solid	315	Yellowish green	17.71 (17.95)	62.52 (62.39)	5.70 (5.50)	8.80 (8.56)	-	-
6.	1 + Na(OAr) (0.300, 0.98)	[(μ-OAr) ₂ Ni ₂ {η ² -(pbz)} ₂] (1d) 0.325 (0.372), 87 crystalline	320	Brown powdered	15.33 (15.61)	60.97 (60.62)	4.13 (3.99)	11.24 (11.17)	-	-
7.	1 + Na{Al(OPr ^t) ₄ } (0.300, 0.98)	[[Al(OPr ^t) ₄]{Ni{η ² -(pbz)}]} (1e) 0.481 (0.525), 91 solid	295	Brown powdered	11.01 (11.06)	65.97 (65.54)	8.17 (8.48)	5.18 (5.27)	-	5.11 (5.08)

^aNeither melt nor decomposed, ^ddecomposition point.

where OPrⁱ for (1c) and OAr for (1d)

Scheme 1. Synthesis and reaction of [(μ-Cl)₂Ni₂{η²-(pbz)₂}] (1).

planar which can be distinguished by transitions¹⁰ in the range near IR to visible region. The octahedral nickel(II) complexes generally exhibit three transitions :

cm⁻¹, 6000–7000 cm⁻¹ and 14000–20000 cm⁻¹ respectively. Tetrahedral nickel(II) complexes are attributable to charge transfer absorption tailing into the visible region to ultraviolet. It has been observed mainly in the complexes having coordinated bromide or iodide ions. The planar geometry is most preferred for the nickel(II)

complexes. However, it is capable of exhibiting tetrahedral geometry as well, specifically in high spin $3d^8$ system.

The electronic spectrum of $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-}(\text{pbz})\}_2]$ (1) complex has been measured in DMF/THF, which exhibits two types of bands, d-d transition bands and charge transfer bands. The observed electronic absorptions in the range $25974\text{--}27174\text{ cm}^{-1}$, corresponds to ${}^3A_{2g} \xrightarrow{\nu_3} {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transition, which is characteristic for the octahedral geometry¹¹⁻¹³ around nickel(II).

The bands observed in the range of $28409\text{--}29940\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be attributable to the charge transfer transitions from phenolate moieties to the central metal nickel(II) ($\epsilon \approx 13000\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$). In addition to above bands, two intense bands are also observed in the range $31250\text{--}34129\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to intraligand charge transfer transition ($\epsilon \approx 15000\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$).

Magnetic studies :

High spin nickel(II) complex show paramagnetism corresponding to two unpaired spin only value, $\mu_{s.o.} = 2.8$ B.M. The magnetic moment is generally observed in the range $3.5\text{--}4.2$ B.M. for tetrahedral geometry^{14,15}. This higher value of magnetic moment may be due to some orbital contribution¹⁶. However, in the case of octahedral nickel(II) complex, magnetic moment value lie in the range $2.8\text{--}3.4$ B.M. Magnetic moment values for monochloro- $\{2\text{-}(o\text{-hydroxyphenyl})\}\text{-benzimidazolato-nickel(II)}$, $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.34$ B.M., which is less than the spin only value for nickel(II) system. Whereas for $[\text{Ni}\{\eta^2\text{-}(\text{pbz})\}_2]$ (2) complex magnetic moment observed is 3.19 B.M., which is in agreement with high spin complex.

FAB-MS studies :

The FAB-MS spectrum (Fig. 1) of mono- $\{2\text{-}(o\text{-hydroxyphenyl})\}\text{-benzimidazolato-nickel(II) chloride}$, $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-}(\text{pbz})\}_2]$ (1), a newly synthesized compound of nickel(II), $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-}(\text{pbz})\}_2]$ (1) (Scheme 2), showed an important molecular ion peak at $m/z = 608$, which correspond to molecular weight of the compound supported for the dimeric structure. Besides this peak, the complex showed the fragmentation ion peak at $m/z = 304$ indicating fragmentation of dimer molecule to monomer¹. Other important peaks were observed as a result of fragmentation of ligand from the complex by the formation of radical cations such as Cl^\bullet , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}^\bullet$ (I); $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}^\bullet$, $\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{NO}^\bullet$, NiCl_2 (II); $\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{NO}^\bullet$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}^\bullet$ (III).

Thermogravimetric studies :

Thermogravimetric analysis is one of the important

techniques for the studies of the thermal reactions sequence of simple and complex compounds. The complex, bis- $\{2\text{-}(o\text{-hydroxyphenyl})\}\text{-benzimidazolato-nickel(II)}$ supports the formula assigned as $[\text{Ni}\{\eta^2\text{-}(\text{pbz})\}_2]$ (2); $\text{NiC}_{26}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$ (molecular weight = 478.71). Initial weight was taken 7.80 mg and final weight found to be 1.10 mg, and the total weight loss was 6.70 mg. This complex has found to be thermally stable up to temperature $240\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. On heating the sample above $240\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ it starts losing weight gradually and decomposes rapidly above $320\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and completely converted to nickel oxide at $600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The first decomposition DTG peak is very strong whereas 2nd and 3rd are medium and broad. These indicate the three consecutive decomposition steps.

For the 1st decomposition stage, loss expected for the residual product is 52% and it has been found to be 50% , and 2nd decomposition stage corresponds the loss for the proposed product is approximately 18.5% and it has been found to be 18% , whereas in the 3rd stage of decomposition almost same loss of residual product corresponds to the weight for NiO.

During the present course of investigation a new bimetallic hydrocarbon soluble complex $[\{(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_2\}\text{Ni}\{\eta^2\text{-}(\text{pbz})\}]$ (1e) has been isolated as a result of the reaction of complex 1 with $\text{Na}\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}$ in $1 : 1$ molar ratio which has two metal centre bridged by isopropoxy groups.

A definite conclusion regarding the structure of these complexes in solid state would be possible only after single X-ray crystallographic studies, which have not been successful so far. However, formula of the complex 1 has been suggested by elemental analysis, spectral studies and confirmed by FAB-MS spectrum showing multiplets representing successive degradation of the molecule 1 shown in Scheme 2 and was found to be dimeric.

Experimental

All chemicals used throughout the course of experimental work were of G.R. or AnalaR grade. Spectroscopic grade solvents were employed for recording the spectra. Benzene (B.D.H.), isopropanol (B.D.H.), tetrahydrofuran (Loba) and pyridine (Loba) were dried according to standard literature procedure. Aluminium isopropoxide¹⁷ was prepared by dissolving aluminium foil in isopropanol in the presence of HgCl_2 as catalyst and refluxing it for ~ 6 h. Final product was purified by distillation (b.p. $95\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Analysis of compound for the quantitative determination of nickel was carried out by atomic absorption spectroscopy, GBC-932 AA. Aluminium con-

Fig. 1. FAB-MS spectrum of $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-(pbz)}\}_2]$ (1).

Scheme 2. Fragmentation pattern of $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-(pbz)}\}_2]$ (1) using FAB-MS spectrum.

tent present in the bimetallic complex was determined after precipitating aluminium as its oxinate¹⁸. Chloride content was estimated by Volhard's method¹⁸. Isopropoxide content in the corresponding isopropoxy derivative was estimated by an oxidimetric method¹⁹. IR spectrum was recorded for complex **1** (in KBr pellets), using Perkin-Elmer 1000 FT-IR spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra of the compounds were recorded in benzene and tetrahydrofuran/pyridine due to solubility problem on a Hitachi-220 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at room temperature (23.5 °C) by Gouy method. FAB-MS spectra of nickel(II) complexes were recorded on JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/data system using argon/xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB-gas. TGA analysis was performed on Stanton Red Craft T.G. balance model-370 with recorder operating on 1 mV full scale with heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ in static air atmosphere.

(A) Preparation of ligands :

The ligand {2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzimidazole, pbzH, Schiff bases (sb= sapH and smabH), sodiumtetraalkoxyaluminate, [Na{Al(OPrⁱ)₄}] were prepared by reported methods²⁰⁻²².

(B) Synthesis of monochloro complex, [(μ-Cl)₂Ni₂{η²-(pbz)}₂] (**1**) :

A freshly prepared aqueous ethanolic solution (50% ethanol, ~50 cm³) of nickel(II) chloride (3.392 g, 14.3 mmol) was added dropwise to a prestirred hot ethanol (~75 cm³) solution containing {2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzimidazole (3 g, 14.30 mmol) in 1 : 1 molar ratio, which produced light pink coloured precipitate [(μ-Cl)₂Ni₂{η²-(pbz)}₂] (**1**) (Scheme 1). The complex (4.250 g, 98%) so obtained, was digested (~1 h), filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and dried at 100 °C under reduced pressure. The product on analysis was found to have Ni, 19.19%; Cl, 12.11%; (calcd.) : Ni, 19.33%; Cl, 11.69%.

(C) Synthesis of complex, [Ni{η²-(pbz)}₂] (**2**) :

An aqueous ethanolic solution of nickel(II) chloride (1.2 g in 30 ml of 50% ethanol) was added to a hot ethanolic solution of the {2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzimidazole (2.3 g in 75 ml ethanol) in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The yellow precipitate of the complex was separated immediately and a dilute solution of sodium acetate was added dropwise to the above solution with constant stirring. Further, it was digested on water bath for ~30 min and filtered. The separated yellow coloured solid complex was washed with ethanol and dried in air.

(D) Reactions of [(μ-Cl)₂Ni₂{η²-(pbz)}₂] (**1**) with Na(smab) :

To a stirred hot yellowish green suspension of monochloro-{2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzimidazolatonickel(II) complex (**1**) (0.300 g, 0.99 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (~30 cm³), sodium salt of salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene (0.23 g, 0.99 mmol) in equimolar ratio was added. The reaction mixture was allowed to reflux for ~1 h, during which time the colour of the solution changed from yellowish green to green. The precipitated NaCl (0.057 g, 1.15 mmol) was removed by filtration. The solvent was removed from the filtrate under reduced pressure to afford solid product [(smab)Ni{η²-(pbz)}] (**1a**) (0.465 g, 98%) (Scheme 1) which was purified by recrystallisation from THF-C₆H₆ mixture. Analysis of this derivative was done Ni, 12.09%; (calcd.) : Ni 12.27%.

Similar procedure was used to isolate [(sap)Ni{η²-(pbz)}] (**1b**), [(μ-OPrⁱ)₂Ni₂{η²-(pbz)}₂] (**1c**), [(μ-OAr)₂Ni₂{η²-(pbz)}₂] (**1d**) and [(μ-OPrⁱ)₂Al(OPrⁱ)₂]Ni{η²-(pbz)}] (**1e**). The synthetic and analytical details of all these complexes are given in Table 1.

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